

Teachers', Students' and Parents' Perceptions on ICT Utilization in Senior Secondary Schools.

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Abstract

The study examined teachers', students' and parents' perceptions on ICT utilization in government secondary schools in Akure South Local Government area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Two hundred (200) Senior Secondary School students, one hundred (100) teachers and fifty (50) parents were randomly selected from 7 public secondary schools of the area. A self-designed questionnaire titled "Parents', Teachers' and Students' Perception towards the use of ICT Questionnaire (PTSPICQ)" was developed, validated and administered on the participants. The reliability of the instrument using Cronbach alpha coefficient was 0.826. Four hypotheses were tested. Data collected were analyzed using ANOVA coupled with descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation which served as precursor to testing the four hypotheses for the study using an independent samples t-test. The result revealed that there was a significant difference in the perceptions among parents, teachers and students towards the use of ICT in senior secondary schools ($F = 31.552$; $P < 0.05 = 3.07$). However, the mean of students' and teachers' perception were significantly higher than of parents' perception. The findings showed that parents, teachers and students understanding of the use of ICT was still below expectation. Relevant recommendations were suggested to improve the observed situation with the recognition of ICT and its importance in education.

Key words: Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in schools; stakeholders' perceptions on ICT utilization in schools, Nigeria

Introduction

In the last two decades, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been reshaping how the world communicates. Today, ICT has radically changed the way we conceived and implement ideas. It has created new forms of socialization and new approaches to the way human interactions take place. In field of education, ICT has revolutionized the process of teaching and learning (Egbedokun & Oyewusi, 2014). Technology involves the generation of knowledge and processes to develop systems that solve problems and extend human capabilities. In other words, technology can change or alter how people

access, gather, analyze, present, transmit, and simulate information (Ajayi & Ekundayo, 2009). The impact of technology is one of the most critical issues in education. The use of information and communication technology (ICT) creates a powerful learning environment and it transforms the learning and teaching process in which students deal with knowledge in an active, self-directed and constructive (Vuorela, 2024). ICT is not just regarded as a tool, which can be added to or used as a replacement of existing teaching methods. ICT is seen as an important instrument to support new ways of teaching and learning. It should be used to develop student's skills for cooperation, communication, problem solving and lifelong learning (Voogt & Pelgrum, 2023). Moreover, technology has not been implemented to transform but to maintain and support the existing practices; according to Cuban (2011), most teachers that use technology tailor the use to fit the familiar practices, not to revolutionize them. Salomon (2022) wrote that the technology used has not affected the educational process and the pedagogical practice of daily life in school to produce outcomes such as independent and deliberate thinkers, lifelong learning skills, and the capacity for solving complex problems alone and in teams, the capacity for adjusting to rapid changes in employment patterns, technology, and required skills. So although ICT is used in classrooms, neither a high level nor innovative pedagogical practices are self-evident (Lehtinen, Sinko, & Hakkarainen, 2021). Empirical studies in schools and classrooms give evidence supporting the conclusion that there are still several shortcomings in implementing ICT, compared to expectations. A Nordic comparative study (Pedersen et al., 2020), an American multiple case study by Ganesh & Berliner(2025) and a Canadian study among teachers and administrators (Gibson & Oberg, 2024), show that ICT is not used to transform teaching methods but to support the teaching of domain content, while the use of ICT in schools is monotonous.

Teachers adopt ICT mainly in the existing practices of their subject subculture (John, 2005), supporting their existing teaching practices (Kaisto, Hämäläinen, & Järvelä, 2017). Technology experiences in school have not used the transformative power of educational technology; the experiences had not been especially exciting for students, the drill and practice exercises were the most common type of exercises (Smeets & Mooij, 2021), and students used technology during their leisure time more actively, richly, and more extensively (Ching, Basham,& Fang 2015; Vuorela, 2024). For example, the Internet was used infrequently and it was used mainly for information search without students practicing information organization and analysis (Gibson & Oberg, 2024; Jedeskog & Nissen, 2024), with students being more often consumers than producers, working more often alone than collaboratively. Students still worked with facts and skills instead of understanding e.g., through collaborative discussion, and teacher-centered instruction was the norm, even in the computer-based classes (Cuban, 2011).

Statement of the problem

The place of Information Communication Technology (ICT) in education has been pointed out but its utilization has not been embraced in appropriately in Nigerian secondary schools. This might not be far from the notions about ICT utilization in the area of this research. The study therefore sought to investigate parents', teachers' and students' perceptions on ICT utilization in selected senior secondary schools in Akure South Local Government area of Ondo State, Nigeria., this is because their perceptions could likely influence the acceptability and utilization of ICT.

Hypotheses

- (i) There is no significant difference in the perception of students, teachers and parents towards utilization of ICT in secondary Schools.
- (ii) There is no significant difference between the perception of students and teachers towards utilization of ICT in secondary Schools.
- (iii) There is no significant difference between the perception of teachers and parents towards utilization of ICT in secondary Schools.
- (iv) There is no significant difference between the perception of students and parents towards utilization of ICT in secondary Schools.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The target population comprised of all students, parents and teachers in Akure South Local Government area of Ondo State. Three hundred and fifty respondents (200 students, 100 teachers and 50 parents) were randomly selected from 7 government owned schools. A questionnaire, titled "Teachers', Students' and Parents' Perception towards utilization of ICT Questionnaire (TSPPICTQ) was developed by the researcher for data collection. The questionnaire was inspired by ideas from reviewed literature and information from pilot study. The instrument contained two sections. Section A collected Demographic characteristic. Section B had Fifteen (15) structured items to measure the perceptions of students, teachers and parents towards utilization of ICT. Section B was structured along four (4) points modified Likert scale format involving the following values: 4-Strongly Agree, 3-Agree, 2-Disagree and 1- Strongly Disagree. Data collected were analyzed using Analysis of Variance and t-test.

Result and discussion

The sequence of the presentation and discussion is in accordance with that of the study hypotheses.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the perception of students, teachers and parents towards utilization of ICT in secondary schools.

Table 1: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA): comparing the perception of students, teachers and parents towards the utilization of ICT in Secondary Schools.

	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F	Significant	Remark
Between Groups	40.649	2	20.325	31.552	3.07	Significant
Within Groups	223.525	347	0.644			
Total	264.174	349				

Table 1 shows that there was a significant difference in the perception of students, teachers and parents towards utilization of ICT in sampled secondary schools. It was therefore important to examine the details of the significant differences by post- hoc-test.

Table 2: Post- hoc-test comparing the perception of students, teachers and parents towards utilization of ICT

(I) Grouping Factors or variable	(J) grouping Factors or variable	Mean difference	Std. error	Sig.	Remark
Student	Teachers	.095	.100	.714	NS
	Parents	-.935*	.068	.000	*
Teachers	Students	-.095	.100	.714	NS
	Parents	-1.030*	.078	.000	*
Parents	Students	.935*	.068	.000	NS
	Teachers	1.1030	.078	.000	*

NS = not Significant at $P < 0.05$

*=Significant at $P < 0.05$

Post-hoc-test indicated that there was no significant difference between teachers' and parents' perceptions towards utilization of ICT. However, there was a significant difference between students' and parents' perceptions. Also, there was a significant difference between students' and teacher'' perceptions towards utilization of ICT.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of students and teachers towards utilization of ICT in secondary schools.

Table 3: t-test analysis comparing students' and teachers' perceptions

	N	mean	Std.dev.	Std. error mean	df	t	p	Remark
students	200	2.09	0.912	0.064	298	1.992	1.960	Significant
teachers	100	1.68	0.665	0.066				

p<0.05

Table 3 reveals that t value of 1.992 is greater than critical value of 1.96. In consequence, hypothesis 2 is confirmed significant. Students demonstrated greater perception toward utilization of ICT in secondary schools than the teachers.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the perception of teachers and parents towards utilization of ICT in secondary schools.

Table 4: t-test analysis comparing teachers' and parents' perceptions

	N	mean	Std.dev.	Std. error mean	df	t	p	Remark
teachers	100	1.68	0.665	0.066	148	1.183	1.960	Not significant
parents	50	1.54	0.706	0.100				

p<0.05

Table 4 reveals that there was no significant difference between teachers' and parents' perceptions towards utilization of ICT. Teachers and parents had similar perceptions towards utilization of ICT.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between the perception of students and parents towards utilization of ICT in secondary Schools.

Table 5: T-test analysis comparing students' and parents' perceptions

	N	mean	Std.dev.	Std. error mean	df	T	P	Remark
students	200	2.09	0.912	0.064	248	3.963	1.960	Significant
parents	50	1.54	0.706	0.100				

P<0.05

Table 5 shows that there was a significant difference between students' and parents' perceptions towards utilization of ICT in secondary schools.

Discussion

This study examined Parents', Teachers' and Students' perceptions on ICT utilization in secondary schools in Akure South Local Government area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Findings showed that there was a significant difference in the perception of students, teachers, and parents towards utilization of ICT and that students had strong mean perceptions toward the use of ICT in secondary schools. Students' perceptions in this compartment indicate that students might think the computer is the absolute solution to their learning problems or the computer might be an essential precondition to their learning problem. Students' perceptions in this way were similar to the characteristics of "Digital Natives" or "Net Generations" (Prensky, 2021). Several researchers explained that Digital Natives had spent their entire lives surrounded by and using computers, digital music, cell phones and all the other toys and tools of digital age. They also maintained that the Digital culture and environment in which the natives had grown up had changed the way they think and therefore the way they perceive teaching and learning. Digital Natives rely heavily on communication technologies to access information and they have a low tolerance to teaching/instruction by the teachers. However, their perceptions are in dissonance with the propositions (Clark, 1999; Sarfo & Elen, 2017) that effective instructional design by the teacher rather than media (computer) is the better means of achieving quality learning.

The result of the finding also revealed that there was no significant difference between teachers' and parents' perceptions toward utilization of ICT in secondary schools. This is an indication that teachers and parents have similar perception towards utilization of ICT. According to the findings of this study, teachers are likely to enhance student's interest in computing as a discipline if they utilize learner-centered

approaches possibly the latter are more compatible with young people everyday experience with ICT. The teachers whose perceptions are in line with the use of computer might think that there is the need to cope with the technological changes in teaching and learning. On the other hand, the teachers whose perceptions are in dissonance with the use of computer can be attributed to the fact that, as pointed out by Means (1994), teachers feared that they would be replaced by computers. In other words, the perceptions of teachers in this way are in line with the characteristics of "Digital Immigrants" (Prensky, 2021). Digital Immigrants lack technological literacy and they are foreigners in Digital lands of the net generation. The results suggest that in Akure South Local Government area of Ondo State, Nigeria, to some degree, students and teachers have different perceptions with respect to the utilization of Computers.

A major finding of this study was that the provision of ICT facilities in the schools though inadequate had high prospects based on the foundation already established. The efforts of the state government, the World Bank and other funding agencies in making the use of ICT mandatory in all public secondary schools through the provision of ICT facilities and alternative supply of electricity to power ICT facilities is commendable. The low level or nonexistence of modern ICT facilities in public schools had been traced to the general lukewarm attitude of government towards education. Ajayi and Ekundayo (2009) previously discovered that ICT facilities such as computers, projectors, electronic notice boards, internet film scripts were not available in most Nigerian secondary schools. They posited that inadequate funding of the schools by the government constitutes a major factor. It is sad to note that in this technological age, internet facilities were non-existent in public schools prior to the World Bank intervention.

Recommendations

Based on the empirical findings of this study and the persistent disparities in stakeholder perceptions and infrastructure, rather than offering isolated computer literacy sessions, the Ondo State Ministry of Education should institutionalise continuous professional development focused on the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework. This ensures that "Digital Immigrant" teachers do not just learn basic computer skills, but actively understand how to integrate digital tools into learner-centered, subject-specific pedagogy. To address the critical deficit in student-to-computer ratios and the unreliability of the national grid, the state government must look beyond international aid. Strategic collaborations with telecommunication firms and local tech hubs should be brokered to supply solar-powered ICT laboratories and zero-rated educational internet access to public secondary schools. Given that parents demonstrated the lowest mean perception and understanding of ICT's academic utility, schools must actively bridge this gap. School Governing Boards and Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) should co-organize "Digital Literacy Awareness Days" to educate parents on how home-based ICT access

supports independent student learning and career readiness. The Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) and secondary school administrators should transition from rigid teacher-centered formats to blended learning models. Developing accessible, offline-capable digital repositories aligned with the national curriculum will empower students to utilize their high digital affinity for structured learning rather than unguided web browsing. To prevent the routine abandonment of donated or government-supplied hardware, every educational zone within the Senatorial District should feature a dedicated ICT maintenance unit. Ensuring that schools have rapid access to technical support will protect financial investments and prevent infrastructural decay.

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